

SMART FATIGUE DETECTION AND HEALTH MONITORING SYSTEM FOR ASSEMBLY LINE WORKERS USING IOT AND COMPUTER VISION TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT: Ensuring the safety and health of assembly line workers is critical to increasing productivity and preventing accidents. This research presents a real-time monitoring system that combines computer vision (AI), wearable Internet of Things (IoT) devices, and cloud-based technologies to detect worker fatigue and health risks. The system calculates eye aspect ratio (EAR) and mouth aspect ratio (MAR) to identify fatigue symptoms such as eye closure and yawning, while wearable IoT devices monitor physiological parameters such as heart rate (HR) and blood oxygen saturation (SpO₂) to detect potential health issues. Alerts are automatically triggered based on pre-defined thresholds, allowing for immediate intervention. All data is processed in real-time with input from wearables and computer vision, and transmitted to a cloud platform for analysis, reporting and storage. This integration of AI-powered computer vision, wearable IoT and cloud connectivity ensures continuous monitoring and provides actionable insights to supervisors, improving workplace safety and operational efficiency. The results of the study demonstrate the effectiveness of this innovative system in identifying fatigue and health issues, reducing accidents and promoting a safer working environment. By using the latest technology, the proposed solution addresses the urgent need for advanced safety measures in demanding work environments.

KEYWORDS: Occupational Health and Safety, Assembly Line, Fatigue Monitoring, IoT, Computer Vision, Industry 4.0.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rise of Industry 4.0, characterized by the integration of IoT, Big Data Analytics, and AI, has significantly improved manufacturing efficiency and productivity (Fordal, 2023). However, these advancements have also introduced concerns regarding worker well-being in smart factory environments (Bottani, 2021). Workplace physical fatigue has been linked to reduced productivity, job dissatisfaction, absenteeism, and severe health risks, including chronic diseases and immune system compromise (Lerman, 2012; Caldwell, 2019; Van der Hulst, 2003). Figure 1. highlights the diseases associated with occupational fatigue (Chan, 2011; Adane, 2013; Tadesse, 2016; Caruso, 2008; Van der Hulst, 2003; Collins, 2009; Melamed S. K., 1992; Melamed S. S., 2006). To address these challenges, predictive analytics is being used to analyze real-time data and identify fatigue-related patterns, enabling early intervention and prevention strategies (Lambay, 2024). Additionally, smart wearable

devices, such as fitness trackers and smartwatches, offer real-time monitoring of workers' physiological data, including heart rate, body temperature, and signs of drowsiness, helping to detect and mitigate fatigue-inducing conditions (Kim J. L., 2024; Shukla, 2025; Adão Martins, 2021). These devices also provide insights into human factors, which influence worker performance and well-being, and identify ergonomic risks like musculoskeletal disorders (Moshawrab, 2022; Mao, 2023). Being non-invasive and automated, wearable technology facilitates continuous monitoring without disrupting workflows (Kamišalić, 2018). By combining advanced automation and human-machine collaboration, smart factories can foster safer, more sustainable workplaces while enabling workers to monitor and manage their health and performance in real-time. Moreover, Industry 5.0 aims to transform manufacturing companies from a technology-centric approach to a people-centric approach, sustainable and resilient manufacturing (Abdous, 2023). The main objective of this research is to propose an

intelligent fatigue detection system within the context of smart manufacturing. This system has been designed with the specific purpose of identifying individuals who are fatigued, specifically in assembly line environments. Worker fatigue can be attributed to multiple reasons, such as repetitive tasks, excessive standing or static positions, manual labor, irregular work shifts and the cognitive stress of monotonous and high-velocity processes (Kim J. W., 2022; Berlin, 2021). The proposed system thereby supporting managers and supervisors in ensuring the safety and productivity of workers on assembly lines. The system uses cutting-edge technologies such as Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Internet of Things (IoT) to provide a fine-grained estimation of how much work has fatigued a worker by assessing the features including physiological data and facial expressions. Yawning or drowsiness generally tends to be considered

universal indicators of fatigue (Yi, 2023), hence this forms an important part in system's the detection process. To complement this system, integration with real-time physiological monitoring via a wearable sensor has been achieved, enabling the fatigued employee to be rapidly noted, enabling the supervisor in turn to take timely action. It is this type of scenario that ensures the well-being of workers, maintains safety levels and keeps productivity levels high on assembly lines. This article is organized as follows. Section 2 discusses the Literature Review discusses the latest research in smart factories, advances in worker fatigue prediction; Section 3 presents our proposed system and methodology; Section 4 the Experimental Results are discussed; Section 5 concludes with considerations of future work.

Fig. 1 Diseases Associated with Occupational Fatigue

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

This section explores how new technologies are transforming the traditional manufacturing and assembly lines, into factories of the future through industry 4.0 technologies such as IoT, big data analytics, and digital twins. Additionally, the section reviews relevant works that focus on monitoring worker fatigue in assembly lines using IoT and Artificial Intelligence. Finally, the section concludes by looking at the need for the proposed system and how it can be achieved.

2.1 Smart Factories

Smart factories are manufacturing systems that enhance the entire production processes with modern concepts such as the Internet of Things, big data, Artificial Intelligence, and automation. These systems employ a network of connected sensors, devices, and machines to produce a huge amount of data in real-time (Wang, 2021). Various measures are then taken to analyze the data in order to reveal trends and optimize the processes as well as the quality of products. Figure 2. illustrates the overall

processes of optimization, production, maintenance in smart factories, there are various technologies that work together. The Internet of Things (IoT) enables interconnection and data exchange between devices, sensors, and objects, integrating tools like machine performance sensors, robots, and RFID technology to monitor goods and material flow. IoT supports Prognostics and Health Management (PHM) systems to prevent equipment breakdowns.

Fig. 2 Industry 4.0 technologies in smart factories

As noted in (Sarkar, 2019), big data technologies in smart factories leverage vast structured and unstructured data to enhance inventory management, supply movement, and predictive maintenance through analytics and pattern recognition.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is used to refer to any computational machine which can perform any task that mimics human intelligence including but not limited to, problem solving, learning and decision making. The application of AI in smart factories is to automate processes, optimize production and enhance quality control. For instance, AI robots can carry out intricate procedures to a very high degree of accuracy and consistency thus minimizing the chances of human errors (Leberruyer, 2023). In addition, to assist some defect for their product, new age solutions like digital twins assist in creating a replica of an actual physical process into a virtual system (Verna, 2024). This latter method can minimize the possibilities of mistakes or the wastage of resources in the actual manufacturing system and improve the efficiency of the entire factory as well. In recent work done by (Friederich, 2022), a production scheduling system of smart factories using digital twin concepts was presented. A digital twin was deployed to enhance and manage production operations, thus facilitating improvements in the scheduling of resources. The study (Bagassi, 2020) explored AR-based human-machine interaction for intelligent airport control towers, noting its intuitive data visualization benefits. However, challenges with spatial visualization and unreliable head-mounted displays for safety-critical tasks highlight the need for further research and user-focused design improvements. In this study (Paredes-Astudillo, 2020) a Human-Centered Scheduling Systems using cyber-physical production systems, for example, may adapt task schedules dynamically within agent-based environments, depending on available information about the cognitive fatigue of the workers using sensor devices directed to measure physiological states. Adoption of these systems decreased cognitive fatigue considerably, positively affecting the general well-being of workers and their productivity levels.

2.2 Worker's Physical Fatigue Monitoring in Assembly Line

Assessing the physical fatigue of assembly line workers is vital for enhancing their efficiency as well as guaranteeing their safety.

Recent advancement in technology have given rise to modern methodologies of monitoring the level of fatigue, which are not restricted to traditional survey-based methods.

Researchers in (Chen, 2023) have developed a system that uses commercially available smartwatches to monitor worker fatigue using IoT and IA. These smartwatches collect data such as heart rate and activity levels, which are analyzed to predict fatigue with 85% accuracy. This system helps reduce human error caused by fatigue and improves efficiency by ensuring that workers remain alert and productive. Another research conducted by (Pilati, 2023) proposes a digital IoT architecture utilizing a superficial electromyography wearable to monitor muscular contractions and recognize fatigue status in assembly line workers, enhancing their physical resilience and well-being during production cycles through continuous monitoring. In the other hand the presence of noise in measurements can affect the reliability of the data collected, which may lead to inaccurate assessments of worker fatigue and ergonomic exposure.

Authors in (Ahmad, 2024) proposes a Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) technology, specifically the Event-Related Potential (ERP) technique with EEG, to monitor assembly line workers' physical fatigue in real-time, addressing limitations of traditional methods like questionnaire surveys that often under-report fatigue levels. The study relies heavily on Brain-Computer Interface (BCI) technology and Electroencephalography (EEG) for real-time fatigue assessment. However, this dependence may limit its applicability in environments where such technology is not readily available or feasible to implement.

This study (Papoutsakis, 2022) investigated using low-cost sensors, like passive cameras and smartwatches, to monitor worker fatigue and ergonomic risks on assembly lines, achieving over 70% accuracy in detecting musculoskeletal disorders and fatigue. However, it identified a time lag (100-120 seconds) between physical strain and heart rate elevation, which could hinder real-time monitoring and timely intervention.

Another study by (Fu, 2019) utilized wearable sensors to continuously monitor muscle fatigue in assembly workers, revealing increased average EMG amplitude and decreased median frequency over the workday, alongside rising perceived fatigue in various muscle regions, aiding real-time fatigue management. However, the study did not account for various environmental factors that could influence muscle fatigue, such as temperature, humidity, and ergonomic conditions of the workspace. These factors can significantly impact worker performance and fatigue levels, and their absence in the study may limit the applicability of the findings to different settings.

Worker fatigue monitoring is crucial for safety and productivity enhancement in assembly lines. Advancements in IoT systems, wearables technology can predict fatigue based on physiological metrics like heart rate. To address this, an integrated solution combines IoT with artificial intelligence to capture real-time physiological parameters and analyze facial expressions to recognize cognitive fatigue signs. This approach not only protects workers' health but also enhances assembly line efficiency by enabling prompt actions and monitoring processes.

3 PROPOSED SYSTEM AND METHODOLOGY

To minimize risk related to drowsiness, numerous experiments conducted in laboratories have indicated that Heart Rate and oxygen saturation (SpO2) may be useful indicators for evaluating alertness, particularly in terms of reaction time performance during both total and partial sleep deprivation caused by physical fatigue (Chua, 2012; Henelius, 2014; Kaida, 2007; Jeklin, 2021). Furthermore, (Hidalgo-Muñoz, 2018) finds that there is evidence indicating a correlation between HRV and cognitive workload requirements, as well as the impact of time spent on assembly operations. Moreover, (Ibrahim, 2022) shows that a higher minimum oxygen saturation indicates one of the keys to fatigue.

For this purpose, our proposed system aims for real-time detection and prevention, leveraging IoT

and AI. It requires workers to wear wearable sensors, such as a smartwatch, to measure heart rate (HR) and oxygen saturation (SpO2). The collected data will be visualized and analyzed to determine whether action is necessary or to anticipate risks related to drowsiness or fatigue. In addition, this system is designed and implemented primarily to detect sleep or drowsiness of workers in assembly line environment. By extracting facial features, and physiological parameters we can take measurements to determine fatigue levels. Our methodology uses computer vision to monitor facial key indicators such as Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) for eye blinks and Mouth Aspect Ratio (MAR). A real-time detection and recognition algorithm processes data from the Pi camera connected to the Raspberry Pi microcontroller. In addition, physiological parameters are monitored separately using sensors incorporate to a wearable smartwatch. All components are integrated into an IoT architecture to ensure comprehensive safety monitoring. In order achieve real-time fatigue detection, each zone is provided by a camera and workers at each station would wear a wireless smart watch while working on the assembly line. Figure 3. illustrate the global conceptual of the proposed end-to-end system, demonstrating the complete methodological sequence from data acquisition via sensors to its representation in a cloud-based environment.

Moreover, various hardware components are illustrated in Figures 4. in the following sections.

Fig. 3 General Architecture of the Proposed System

The EAR is accurately calculated using the Raspberry Pi 4 model B and Pi camera modules to perform continuous recording of facial landmarks, which are localized using the facial landmarks

algorithm. The IoT-based system is developed through the integration of certain IoT modules such as a wireless sensor for the hand smart watch, a Pi camera to detect worker sleep or drowsiness. The

sensor modules are then appropriately integrated into the controllers, which intelligently monitor and warn the drowsy worker in real-time via a speaker, while physiological data is sent to cloud storage for future analysis and prevention.

3.1 Component Description

The proposed system encompasses essential components to allow for real-time health monitoring and worker fatigue detection. The Raspberry Pi 4 Model B is a multipurpose single-board computer that has GPIO for sensor interface, high-speed connection, and a 4K dual-display (UZUN, 2021) (Figure 4 a). Pi Camera Module V2: Uses an 8-megapixel Sony sensor to record high-definition photos and movies for face expression analysis (Kulkarni, 2017) (Figure 4 b). For physiological monitoring, the MAX30102 Sensor Module uses photoplethysmography to measure heart rate and SpO₂ (Dhruba, 2021) (Figure 4 c). A low-power Internet of Things module for integrating wearable technology, such as heart rate monitors, is the ESP32-C3-WROOM-02 (Mousavi, 2023) (Figure 4 d). When signs of drowsiness or health risks are identified, the speaker emits voice alerts (Samanta, 2020) (Figure 4 e).

Fig.4 IoT hardware devices

3.2 Monitoring Worker’s Face

The worker’s face is continuously monitored, as shown in figure 2. The detailed steps explained as follows:

3.2.1 Video Capture

The video is recorded using the Raspberry Pi camera integrated with the Raspberry Pi 4. The recorded videos are divided into consecutive frames for facial detection. OpenCV is a programming library focused on real-time computer vision. It helps in capturing live camera footage and is compatible with libraries like Dlib and Mediapipe. OpenCV is essential for model performance by processing live input footage to identify key terms like MAR and EAR. It also allows monitoring and visualization of

MAR and EAR through graphs, aiding in identifying thresholds and monitoring worker’s facial.

3.2.2 MediaPipe Landmark

Shape prediction is a machine learning tool developed by Google (Google, 2024), MediaPipe FaceMesh, which identifies distinct points within facial anatomical structures. It uses Tensorflow.js for seamless implementation across web browsers and devices. The Facial Landmark Algorithm aids in delineating facial features, aiming to discern facial structures through shape prediction methodologies. The 468-point system, depicted in figure 5, categorizes Mediapipe Face attributes using Google's face mesh library. Transfer learning is applied in facial landmark training to concurrently predict 2D semantic contours from real-world data and 3D landmark coordinates from synthetic data. The established network enables precise prediction of 3D landmarks utilizing both synthetic and real-world data.

Fig.5 468-point Face Landmark

3.2.3 Face Detection and Feature Extraction

The application of Mediapipe Face Mesh is crucial for identifying key facial features in this stage. The algorithm focuses solely on facial structures, omitting extraneous elements. The use of Mediapipe FaceMesh is vital for recognizing significant facial attributes to complete this phase. The Mediapipe Face Mesh facial landmark detector generates 468 XY-coordinate points. A shape predictor technique is employed to label these 468 points. The facial region is identified through the application of these points. By examining the arrangement of these points, a representation is generated, as demonstrated in figure 6.

Fig.6 Face Detection in 3D using 468-points landmark

Face feature extraction is a significant method in conjunction with face detection, identifying essential facial landmarks like the eyes, nose, and mouth. Our research on drowsiness detection underscores the necessity of recognizing the eyes and mouth as critical subsequent steps. The 468-point system assigns specific indices for the left eye, right eye, and lips, facilitating precise localization.

In our analysis of worker fatigue detection, emphasis is placed on the eyes and lips from the 468 data points. The eye regions consist of 32 data points, with 16 for each eye, while the mouth comprises 40 data points. The computation of the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) requires only 12 points, with 6 allocated to each eye. Upon review of Figure 5, the selected 12 landmark points are distinctly ordered as E1, E2, E3, E4, E5, and E6.

3.2.4 EAR and MAR Metrics

The vertical and horizontal coordinates of the eye are illustrated in Figure 7. Upon the extraction of both the left and right eye coordinates, these values are subsequently employed in the calculation of the Eye Aspect Ratio through formula (1):

$$EAR = \frac{\|E_2 - E_6\| + \|E_3 - E_5\|}{2\|E_1 - E_4\|} \quad (1)$$

Where E represents the landmark on the eyelids and n represents the position of the landmark.

Fig.7 Eye Vertical and Horizontal Coordinates Landmark

We will employ face mesh algorithm to identify and extract the pertinent landmarks within the eye area (points E1 – E6) as shown in Figure 7. Upon extraction of the pertinent points, the calculation of the Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR) ensues by comparing the eye's height to its width. The EAR generally remains consistent when the eye is open, approaching zero as it closes, a phenomenon that is somewhat individual-dependent and minimally affected by head orientation. The proportion of the open eye exhibits slight variability among persons and remains unaffected by image resizing or facial rotation. Given that eye blinking is a synchronous action of both eyes, the average EAR is calculated for both eyes in equations (2), (3) and (4) below:

$$EAR_L = \frac{\|E_2^L - E_6^L\| + \|E_3^L - E_5^L\|}{2\|E_1^L - E_4^L\|} \quad (2)$$

$$EAR_R = \frac{\|E_2^R - E_6^R\| + \|E_3^R - E_5^R\|}{2\|E_1^R - E_4^R\|} \quad (3)$$

To compute the ultimate Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR), the average of the two EAR values is calculated using equation (4):

$$AVG. EAR = \frac{EAR_L + EAR_R}{2} \quad (4)$$

If range of EAR exceeding 0.25 signifies the worker's eyes being unfastened. The occurrence of worker drowsiness in video frames is attributed to a reduction in the threshold value below 0.25.

The Mouth's Aspect Ratio (MAR) can be calculated using the formula described in (5). MAR requires only 6 points, specifically chosen landmarks designated for the vertical and horizontal coordinates of the mouth: M1, M2, M3, M4, M5, and M6, as illustrated in figure 8 below.

$$MAR = \frac{\|M_2 - M_6\| + \|M_3 - M_5\|}{2\|M_1 - M_4\|} \quad (5)$$

Where M_n represents the landmark on the lips, and n represents the position of the landmark.

Fig.8 Mouth vertical and horizontal coordinates landmark

Similar to the EAR, one can employ the ratio of distances between mouth landmarks to evaluate yawning through a simple mathematical expression. Following the acquisition of individual MARs for the mouth, the average MAR is calculated, if the MAR threshold exceeds 1.2, the worker is classified as yawning.

3.3 Monitoring worker's heart rate and blood oxygen levels

The proposed system framework for monitoring workers' physiological parameters using IoT technology architecture is presented in Figure 9. The system consists of a wearable smartwatch embedded with an MAX30102 sensor and an ESP32-C3-WROOM-02 microcontroller. This smartwatch collects heart rate (HR) and blood oxygen saturation (SpO2) data using light spectroscopy, enabling changes in blood volume in the worker's hand to be measured. The data are transmitted via Wi-Fi, then transferred to the cloud via an API request. Finally, the data is analyzed on the ThingSpeak platform, allowing real-time monitoring and alerts for health risks.

Fig.9 Architecture of a Smartwatch for monitoring workers' health using IoT

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Our system is designed to perform multiple functions simultaneously to monitor both fatigue and health parameters, as shown in Algorithm 1 below. The system uses a Pi Camera and MAX30102 sensor to monitor fatigue and health parameters in real-time. It detects potential drowsiness and health risks using eye closure and yawning detection mechanisms. It also monitors heart rate and blood oxygen saturation, triggering alerts if any threshold is exceeded. The system alerts supervisors and uploads data to the cloud for analysis and reporting.

Algorithm 1: Worker Fatigue and Health Monitoring System

1. Input: EAR, MAR, HR, SpO₂
2. Output: Drowsy, Yawning, or Health Alert
- ~Initialize Thresholds and States:
 3. Eye_Threshold ← 0.25
 4. Mouth_Threshold ← 1.2
 5. HR_Threshold_high ← 100
 6. HR_Threshold_Low ← 50
 7. SpO₂_Threshold ← 90
 8. alarm_status_eye ← False
 9. alarm_status_mouth ← False
 10. alarm_status_health ← False
- ~Eye Closure Detection:
 11. If EAR ≤ Eye_Threshold then:
 12. If alarm_status_eye = False then:
 13. Set alarm_status_eye ← True.
 14. Send "Eye Closure Alert".
 15. End If
 16. Else:
 17. Set alarm_status_eye ← False.
 18. End If
- ~Yawning Detection:
 19. If MAR ≥ Mouth_Threshold then:
 20. If alarm_status_mouth = False then:
 21. Set alarm_status_mouth ← True.
 22. Send "Yawning Alert".
 23. End If

24. Else:
 25. Set alarm_status_mouth ← False.
26. End If

~Health Monitoring:

27. If (HR > HR_Threshold_high OR HR < HR_Threshold_Low OR SpO₂ < SpO₂_Threshold) then:
 28. If alarm_status_health = False then:
 29. Set alarm_status_health ← True.
 30. Send "Health Alert".
 31. End If
32. Else:
 33. Set alarm_status_health ← False.
34. End If

End Algorithm

Using real-time monitoring of metrics (Heart Rate (HR), SpO₂, Mouth Aspect Ratio (MAR), and Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR)), the experiment aimed to identify worker fatigue in an assembly line environment. Based on the observed metrics, the algorithm successfully identified three different alert types: Eye Closure, Yawning and Health Risks. Alarms were set triggered when: EAR dropped below 0.25, indicating drowsiness-induced eye closure as shown in Figure 10. MAR was higher than 1.2, which indicates yawning as shown in Figure 11. SpO₂ fell below 90% or HR was above the 50–100 bpm range, indicating a possible health danger related to fatigue. Data from sensors was sent to the ThingSpeak cloud (Figure 12) every three seconds. The dataset gathered from the cloud for ease of identification, abnormal conditions were highlighted in red, and alarms were noted and documented in an Excel file, as illustrated in Figure 13.

Fig. 11 Yawning Detection

Fig. 12 Data visualization of EAR, MAR, HR, and SpO₂ on the ThingSpeak Cloud

Threshold based visualization charts for EAR, MAR, HR and SpO₂, depicted in Figure 14, provide a clear representation of worker fatigue indicators. Low EAR values indicate possible eye closure, while high MAR values indicate yawning, both common signs of fatigue. Abnormal HR values, either below 50 or above 100, indicate stress or reduced alertness, and SpO₂ values below 90% indicate possible oxygen deprivation affecting overall performance. By monitoring these parameters and identifying threshold violations, the system effectively detects signs of fatigue, enabling timely intervention to improve worker safety and productivity.

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	Workstation 2	EAR	MAR	HR	SpO ₂	Status
2	Workstation 2	0,29	1	64	86	Health Alert
3	Workstation 2	0,25	1,03	40	98	Eye Closure Alert
4	Workstation 2	0,34	1	117	100	Normal
5	Workstation 2	0,26	1,34	66	100	Yawning Alert
6	Workstation 2	0,22	1,05	45	91	Health Alert
7	Workstation 2	0,3	1,12	45	93	Normal
8	Workstation 2	0,28	1,33	77	90	Yawning Alert
9	Workstation 2	0,21	1,2	55	97	Eye Closure Alert
10	Workstation 2	0,4	1,11	105	87	Health Alert
11	Workstation 2	0,27	1,49	46	95	Yawning Alert
12	Workstation 2	0,31	1,45	117	92	Normal
13	Workstation 2	0,26	1,22	57	93	Normal
14	Workstation 2	0,38	1,46	87	98	Normal
15	Workstation 2	0,22	1,43	107	96	Health Alert
16	Workstation 2	0,3	1,44	45	93	Normal
17	Workstation 2	0,31	1,47	82	95	Normal
18	Workstation 2	0,32	1,35	40	94	Health Alert
19	Workstation 2	0,29	1,17	112	85	Normal
20	Workstation 2	0,37	1,16	50	89	Normal
21	Workstation 2	0,34	1,36	106	91	Yawning Alert
22	Workstation 2	0,39	1,01	76	97	Normal

Fig. 13 Dataset

Fig. 14 Line charts of the parameters EAR, MAR, HR and SpO₂ with their thresholds.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The proposed technique successfully employs Artificial Intelligence and Internet of Things technology to incorporate real-time monitoring fatigue in assembly line conditions. The system efficiently detects tiredness and health hazards by monitoring vital indicators like Eye Aspect Ratio (EAR), Mouth Aspect Ratio (MAR), Heart Rate (HR), and SpO₂. This allows the system to promptly issue notifications to ensure worker safety. Data is

sent to the cloud for real-time monitoring and recorded for analysis, offering a dependable and expandable way to improve workplace safety. Future work focus on incorporating machine learning for predictive analytics, adding more health metrics, making wearable devices compatible, and improving scalability for wider industrial applications will be the main goals of future developments. These improvements are intended to produce a more thorough and proactive safety monitoring system.

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